

CASE - Collision Avoidance System Evaluation for agriculture robots

Access link: https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSfG0MtcWsuPuw98-cMei8yLQihOn2B6nQ4Lh9S1_zCdRIUSjQ/viewform?usp=sf_link

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DESCRIPTION

This form has been developed to allow the evaluation of collision avoidance systems in a first stage regarding the type of sensors used, implementation of algorithms, type of computational systems used, code best practices, deep learning, and more, to help developers, researchers and even manufactures in the implementation of their systems.

The evaluation is realized according to standards, high assurance software frameworks for robotics operating system ROS, HAROS, implemented safety architectures for autonomous vehicles in agriculture environments, manufactures know-how, and field tests with robots realized in various conditions.

SECTIONS CONTENT

- Primary Sensor Question: The selection adapts the form to the type of sensor/s used in the Collision avoidance system
 - Collision Avoidance: Questions related to the implementation and features of the system to evaluate basic system operations that can prevent in field issues. Also verifies standards compliance and specifies certain system features to be evaluated in next sections.
 - Obstacle Detection: If present in the system, evaluates methods, data preparation before training and types of neural network scaling to machine learning (ML) implementations, redundancy systems, etc.
 - CPU: Evaluates the usage and implementation of system processor.
 - Code Quality: Evaluates de OS implementation and code reliability running in the system.
 - ROS: if present as the system OS, evaluates the existence of evaluation methods, e.g. code quality, bug test and more, to verify the reliability of the ROS implementation.
 - Other: Evaluates the existence of evaluation methods, e.g. code quality, bug test and more, to verify the reliability of the code implementation.
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EVALUATION SYSTEM

The evaluation system consists of points that are awarded to each question according to its relevance:

IEC / ISO Standards question: 10 points

Additional features question: 7 points

Simple question: 5 points

The relation between the number of points that the CA system got and the total amount of points defines the level that the system is at:

Safe: CA > 90%

Need improvements: 90% > CA > 50%

Unsafe: CA < 50%

EVALUATION ARCHITECTURE

References:

[1] ISO 13849-1:2015 Safety of machinery – Safety-related parts of control systems – Part 1: General principles for design. Geneva, Switzerland: International Organization for Standardization, (2015).

[2] ISO 26262 ASIL

- [3] ISO 3691-4:2020 Industrial trucks – Safety requirements and verification – Part 4: Driverless industrial trucks and their systems. International Organization for Standardization, (2020).
- [4] ISO 13482:2014 Robots and robotic devices – Safety requirements for personal care robots. International Organization for Standardization, (2014).
- [5] Improving the Quality of ROS Applications with HAROS, IROS 2021 Tutorial. <https://haslab.github.io/SAFER/iros21-tutorial.html>
- [6] Rick, S., Rodrigo, Q., Krzysztof, C.: An Analysis of ISO 26262: Using Machine Learning Safely in Automotive Software. Safety of the Intended Functionality, SAE, pp. 13-25, (2017).
<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1709.02435>

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